

THE ROLE OF MODULAR TRAINING IN THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article provides information on the importance of the credit-modular system in the professional training of future technology teachers in higher education. The influence of innovative technologies, which create wide didactic opportunities for personal development, on the development and improvement of the educational process in educational institutions was also discussed.

Key words: echnology, innovation, innovation, technical and technological, credit-modular, competence, modular education, professional mobility, modular technology, didactics.

РОЛЬ МОДУЛЬНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКЕ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация о важности кредитно-модульной системы в профессиональной подготовке будущих учителей технологии в высших учебных заведениях. Также обсуждалось влияние инновационных технологий, создающих широкие дидактические возможности для личностного развития, на развитие и совершенствование образовательного процесса в образовательных учреждениях.

Ключевые слова: технология, инновация, новшество, технико-технологическое, кредитно-модульное, компетентность, модульное образование, профессиональная мобильность, модульная технология, дидактика.

The rapid development of higher education in our republic as a result of the social needs of the society and the entry into the world educational space has led to a change in the main directions of educational activities in higher education institutions. One of the most important features of the modern pedagogical process is its technological nature. The division of education into stages and levels, determination of effective ways of joint application of teaching methods and methods, use of multimedia technologies and teacher's skills - all this requires the application of modern teaching technologies in practice.

In this case, significant changes occur not only in the content of pedagogical and educational activities, but also in the structures of the forms of transmission used for educational information and student learning, especially in modular education. Today, our society is in great need of creative, enterprising, educated people. The modern crisis of the education system indicates the existence of a gap between the sharply changed living conditions, society's demands and the education system, its goals, types, content, and teaching technologies. One of the main problems is the slow development of technological education. The technological process is the most important component of social development today because it can respond to social processes.

The improvement of technological education serves as an indispensable condition for the formation of the cultural consciousness of society and its economic well-being. The system of

pedagogic personnel training formed until now requires significant changes. This is related to a number of problems in higher education, we will focus on 3 of these problems:

1. A student of a higher educational institution of pedagogy is assigned the task of acquiring a large amount of knowledge distributed over a number of subjects, but despite this, there is no improvement in the current or final academic results of students;

2. Teachers of general and special subjects constantly complain about the lack of instructional time and its improper distribution;

3. Independence has been given to higher education institutions in the development and approval of science programs, but this does not mean that the teacher's creative energy should be used. (Although the use of a formal format in the development of science programs is limited, the teacher is still limited in the use of his creativity in the development of science programs).

It is known that the traditional system of pedagogic personnel training aimed at learning the content of educational science, methodical manuals and recommendations in the selection and application of different regional methods of teaching does not meet the requirements of school teachers. The majority of teachers emphasize the need to apply innovative technologies to educational practice, including modular teaching and project methods that help increase the effectiveness of educational activities and develop students' creative abilities.

Innovative technologies that create wide didactic opportunities for personal development have a significant impact on the development and improvement of the educational process in educational institutions. Today, the education system is facing complex problems: the volume of knowledge, information and the number of subjects are growing significantly faster than the level of improvement of teaching methods, the new "State Educational Standard of Higher Education". In accordance with the main rules, the number of contact hours has been significantly reduced. Some of these problems will be solved with the help of innovative educational technologies that open the door to new opportunities in the field of education, learning activities and student creativity. The design of new educational technologies ensures the achievement of high quality and guaranteed results in the formation of the teacher's personality. Higher education should create conditions for intellectual, creative and moral development of a person. This is not only the content of education, but also the task of the educational technologies used. Thus, in our opinion, the effectiveness of the professional training of the future technology teacher depends on the development and implementation of technological support tools for the educational process.

Nowadays, there are different technologies. Conditionally, they can be divided into traditional and innovative technologies.

Novation (from English, "novation" - new) - replacing something with a new one. Innovation (from English - "innovation") is a change within the system, an innovation that is implemented at the expense of the system's own ("in"-internal) reserves. Innovation is a unity of ideas, processes, tools and results in qualitative improvement of the pedagogical system.

Traditional educational technology is a technology that is used traditionally, often unconsciously, by example, relying on the method of organizing a lesson in the form of a classroom lesson and illustrative explanation. Traditional education shows authoritarian pedagogical requirements, and teaching in it is weakly connected with the inner life of the student, his diverse demands and needs. In traditional education, there are no conditions that nurture the manifestation of individual abilities and personal creativity. The authoritarianism of the

educational process is manifested in the mandatoryness of the educational procedures and the orientation to the student at the secondary level. In such a system, a student is a subordinate object, a teacher-commander, a judge. The methods of acquiring knowledge are based on the following: delivery of ready-made knowledge, learning based on an example, oral presentation and reproductive reproduction. The educational process is characterized by the lack of independence, the student's weak motivation in the educational activity as an activity in traditional technology.

As stated by V.A.Slastenin, between the increasing number of current scientific, social and political information in the field of the teacher's professional activity, and the old ways of processing, storing and transmitting them, i.e. traditional teaching technology there is a conflict. It is this conflict that creates the need for the introduction of educational technology, based on the personal-activity approach based on critical thinking, problem-viewing and analysis, decision-making, and teamwork skills.

The process of training a modern specialist should not end at a higher education institution, but should be continuous. It is important to teach a person to learn independently, to be able to combine this knowledge and apply it to acquire new knowledge. This cannot be achieved through the traditional education system, where the student gets used to the ready-made presentation of knowledge. If various teaching technologies are used in the educational process, then each student will be involved in active cognitive activities, learn to adapt to changing life situations, think critically, be able to create new ideas, where and knows exactly how the acquired knowledge can be applied in practice.

Each educational technology has its advantages and disadvantages, strengths and weaknesses. The specific characteristics of education as a socio-economic field make special demands on the use of technologies, because their (technologies) impact is focused on people. In this regard, along with the technologicalization of educational activity, the process of its humanization is also inevitable, and this principle is becoming more and more widespread within the framework of the person-oriented approach.

A modern educational technology that implements approaches based on personal activity and competence is modular education. Modular teaching involves not only the acquisition of knowledge by students, but also the methods of acquiring knowledge, as well as the activity of developing a person's perceptive power and creative potential. Let's consider the essence of modular teaching technology.

Modular education appeared after the Second World War, when there was a high need for a training system for professional skills in a relatively short period of time. Industrial problems are studied in detail, and guidelines for their theoretical and technological application are developed. It was a type of modular education, but the term had not yet been adapted to education and professions. More than a decade later, the higher education sector has welcomed the trend of systematizing technical and vocational education on a modular basis. Modular teaching technology appeared in the late 60s as an alternative to traditional educational technology and spread rapidly in higher education institutions in English countries.

The UNESCO conference held in Paris in 1974 prompted the introduction of modular technologies. He recommended the creation of open and flexible structures of education and professional training to adapt to the changing needs of industry and science and to local conditions. To these requirements, modular teaching integrates its own types and forms of education, easily

creating content using parts, students who have the opportunity to independently study the literature offered to them now at their convenience. It was responsive full of characters to create options based on the audience.

There were different views on modular teaching in different countries. For example, in England and Sweden, education is built according to the rules of modularity. According to him, a completed block is understood as a module, more attention is paid to the content of this block than to organizational elements. In America, a module is a part of the school day filled with appropriate didactic content, that is, the main focus is on the organizational aspect. The essence of our modular teaching technology for pedagogy is that in the process of working with the module, the student achieves the specific goals of the educational activity completely independently (or with some help).

However, despite the fact that the new type of education is sufficiently "mature" in terms of content and age, there are still different views on the meaning of the concept of "modular education" and understanding the technology of its construction. A number of foreign authors (B.Goldshmid, M.Goldshmid, etc.) understand the module as the formation of an independent unit of activity that helps to achieve clearly defined goals. Dj. Russell defines the module as an educational package that covers the unity of the educational material and the activities assigned to the learner, resulting in the complete mastery of the educational material. These authors, who are recognized as the founders of modular education, emphasize in their works the importance of increasing the activity of learners in the pedagogical process, which shows that modular technology is an alternative to traditional education that provides passive knowledge to the student. shows.

In the early years of the development of this type of education in the United States and England, the principle of modularity was interpreted based on a set of different materials that could serve as the basis of individual education of students. In this approach, modular learning is actually defined as a "package" learning method.

Analyzing the foreign experience, it can be noted that in the early stages of the development of the modular teaching technology, it is a set of training programs for individual education that ensures the educational achievements of a student with a certain level of preliminary training. recognized as It is implemented by special separate functional links, which are reflected in the content, organizational forms and methods of the modules, whose task is to achieve specific pedagogical goals.

The goal of modular education is to create the most favorable conditions for the development of a person through the flexibility of the educational content, the organization of educational activities in accordance with the individual curriculum, and the ways of ensuring adaptation to the individual needs of the person and the level of his basic training.

The transition to the modular technology of educational organization implies a significant increase in the specific weight and importance of independent work in the educational process, requires a significant increase in the independence, initiative, creativity, social and professional activity of future specialists, this is an activity that requires the implementation of new methodological approaches in solving the problems of pedagogical motivation.

The main goal of credit-module education is the formation of independent learning skills in graduates. In credit-module teaching, the teacher's informative function alternates with counseling

and management functions, while maintaining the leading role within the framework of two-subject relations of the pedagogical process. On the basis of conscious goal setting and self-determination, it is envisaged to build the entire educational process with a hierarchy of immediate, medium (general educational skills and competencies) and prospective (development of individuality) goals.

The active learning process in the credit-module system consists of the following important stages:

- Acceptance of the goal by the student;
- Preparation for understanding a new topic;
- Practical educational activity;
- Structural analysis, creation of evidence;
- Summarizing and evaluating educational results;
- Setting new goals.

According to S.I. Arkhangelsky, modular education is based on the activity approach and the principle of consciousness (perception) (the educational program and the personal learning trajectory are understood), it is characterized by the type of closed management due to the modular program and modules, which makes it highly included in the category of technologies.

The content of credit-module education is made up of an educational module. The educational module includes: a completed information block, a plan of the student's targeted actions, the teacher's advice to ensure the student's development. Modular technology ensures individualization of education, taking into account structural features, level of mastery, level of independence, teaching methods and methods, ways of self-control and ways of management. The goal of credit-module education is to enable learners to develop learning material taking into account individual approaches and to increase their independence.

We approve the opinion of P.A. Yutsevichene, who developed the modular education system relatively deeply. He noted that the essence of the modular teaching technology is that the student can work independently with the individual program offered to him. The individual program includes a targeted action plan, a data bank, and a methodical manual that achieves the specified didactic goals. The teacher's role can vary from information control to counseling.

The purpose of modular educational technology is to help students develop their independence, to form their independent learning skills, and to develop the ability to master learning material taking into account individual methods of learning.

The central concept of the theory of credit-module education is the concept of "module". Despite the maturity of modular education both in terms of content and age, there are still different opinions related to the issues of creating a module and its educational content on construction technology, as well as developing a system of educational forms and methods.

The concept of "module" is used in many fields. One of the main purposes of this term is a functional link. In one of the most common definitions, a module is described as follows: a module is an artificial educational system that reflects the structural, procedural-effective and organizational-management aspects of pedagogical tools necessary for solving tasks.

Module (Latin *Modulus* - measure) 1) In exact sciences: the name of some coefficient or quantities; 2) a complex engineering package that performs its independent function in a technical device (spacecraft module); 3) a separate, relatively independent part of a system or organization.

Dj. Russell, the founder of modular education, defines a module as "a learning package (educational pocket) containing a conceptual unit of learning material and actions to be performed by students."

G. Owen included in the module an individual approach to the student and the teacher, participants of the educational process (teacher + learner), educational material and tools that help ensure their interaction. introduces and understands it as a "closed complex of education".

In the report of the UNESCO conference held in 1982, a module is defined as a separate educational package (educational package) designed for individual or group learning situations for the acquisition of one or a group of skills. is described.

The module is a logically completed part of the educational material, which necessarily accompanies the control of students' knowledge and skills. The working program of the subject is the basis for the formation of modules. The number of modules also depends on the specifics of the subject and the desired frequency of educational supervision.

Analyzing the concept of "modular education", which implements educational modules, we note that in modern pedagogy it is defined as the organization of the educational process, in which educational information is divided into modules (relatively complete and independent units, pieces of data). Allows multiple modules to cover a specific subject or even an entire subject.

Fundamental differences between modular education technology and other technologies:

educational content - modules, which are simultaneously an information bank and a methodical guide for data acquisition - are manifested in completed and independent complexes of educational content;

with the help of modules, it is ensured that the students independently see a certain level of preliminary preparation for each lesson;

in the educational process, equal subject-subjective relations between the teacher and students are inevitably observed;

educational activity is algorithmized;

mastering the material occurs in the course of the completed cycle of educational activities and the variability of the level of complexity is assumed.

The theoretical analysis of modular teaching technology made it possible to highlight the following features:

- development of each component of the didactic system and their visual appearance in the module program and modules is ensured;

- structuring of the educational content, presentation of theoretical material in a careful sequence, methodical material that allows for correction (correction) of the educational process, assessment and control system of mastering level is planned;

- variability of education, adaptation of the educational process to the individual capabilities and requirements of students is envisaged.

In modular teaching, the content of the subject is inextricably linked with the concept of the educational module, because in it the elements of the educational content are logically and systematically connected. According to the conceptual basis (laws, concepts, basic semantic units, terms, categories), control and assessment materials covering all types of educational work on the module are created and are monitored after the module is studied. The most common form of control is testing. Based on the results of the test control, the teacher gives the necessary

recommendations to the students. The control results are also used by students to assess how well they have mastered the learning material, based on the number of points they have collected.

Thus, modular education implies the technology of implementation, that is: the planned result of education, the sequence of learning the content of education, the level of mastery, control of the quality of education. The number of modules will depend on the specifics of the subject and the frequency deemed necessary for the management of education.

The technology of modular teaching, which absorbed the dynamics of the development of modern didactic theories, synthesized their features and thereby made it possible to more successfully combine different approaches to the selection of content, its presentation and methods of organizing the educational process.

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